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Prediction of Forest Fire Area Using Machine Learning Algorithms

Abstract: - Now-a-days occurrence of forest fires has become a common phenomenon due to multiple reasons which are either man-made or natural. The impact on land due to forest fires has been huge lately, specifically in places full of vegetation around the globe that rapidly affect ecosystems around them. This emphasises the urgent need to develop some models which will be able to predict the forest fire leading to better understanding of the components that influence the total burnt areas in specific conditions. Keeping it in mind, the work in this study aims to predict the total area burnt (in acres) due to forest fires by developing different prediction models using six Machine Learning techniques viz. Neural Network, Support Vector Machine, Multi-Layer Perceptron, K-Nearest Neighbour, Decision Tree and Stacking Regressor. Kaggle forest fire dataset has been used to conduct the empirical analysis. This original Kaggle dataset was enhanced and made enriched with the addition of relevant features which played a key role in making the dataset robust, thus leading to accurate predictions. The performance of the prediction models was evaluated using two evaluation measure viz. Mean Absolute Error and R-Squared Error. Correlation heatmaps were also used to the extract the best features from the original dataset as well as enhanced dataset. It was concluded that the prediction models have performed exceptionally well on the enhanced dataset than on the original dataset with Decision Tree technique and Multi-Layer Perceptron technique showing exceptional performances.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Classification, correlation heatmap

1. Introduction

Forest fires can be classified as natural or man-made, and they are connected to land removal and deforestation in tropical, temperate, and boreal forests. Fires that occur due to man-made causes are caused by the unlawful ignition of woods for the aim of acquiring land. On the other hand, natural forest fires are unintentional and are triggered by natural phenomena such as sunlight or lightning [1].

The impact on land due to forest fires has been huge lately, specifically in places full of vegetation around the globe that rapidly affect ecosystems around them. This emphasises the urgent need to increase our efficiency of the prediction of the forest fire and also in better understanding of the components that influence total burned areas in specific conditions, as well as real-time wildfire spread modelling. This necessitates efficient and in-depth data mining of previous wildfire statistics. As global climate conditions are projected to change fast, it is critical to determine the foundational elements determining the harms of forest fires in various regions [2].

Alternative approaches for suppressing, preventing and simulating wildfires continue to emerge. Despite the fact that fires caused by either us or lightning are prevalent, a variety of climatic and ecological conditions affect their propensity to spread. Local climate conditions, the physical features of an area, and type of vegetation are among these considerations. In addition, the state and amount of vegetation per unit area are some of the important components that will influence wildfire behaviour and the long-term effects on agriculture, ecology, the environment, and forestry [1]. Large number of uncontrollable wildfires are due to the windy conditions. In the hills or mountains territories, where localised high winds feed flames, topography and particularly canyons are prone to the wildfire. Wind-driven flames' intermittent and changing heat input, as well as coherent structures within flames influenced by the windy conditions, influence the directions and speeds at which wildfires spread. Smouldering and blazing wildfires have very diverse behaviours, and the spontaneous movement between the two

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states is also impacted by complicated weather and environmental factors [3][4]. The rate at which wildfires spread is determined by a variety of factors, including wind speeds and directions, resulting in a complicated nonlinear number of interactions. The type and condition of lands have an impact on how quickly wildfires spread. Similarly, how forest fires expand to specific places is influenced by wind-driven firebrand transit and the form of the firebrands [5][6].

Keeping the above issues in mind, the authors in this paper aim to develop six reliable models that will be used for predicting the area burnt due to forest fire. The popular Kaggle forest fire Machine Learning dataset has been used to conduct the experimental analysis. This collection has a geographical record of wildfires that occurred in the United States of America (USA) from the years 1992 to 2015 [7]. This dataset has been further enhanced to make it more robust by adding relevant features for all the data points available. A series of pre-processing steps were carried out to filter out a plot of points to get a dataset of dense data points located in the same region. The data points considered in this dataset pertains to Virginia region of USA [8].

Different Machine Learning techniques [9, 10] had been used to develop the prediction models viz. Neural Network, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Decision Tree (DT) and Stacking Regressor. Different performance measures [11] used to evaluate the performance of predicted models were Mean Absolute Error (MAE), R-Squared Error (R2) and Correlation Heatmap.

The paper is organized into five sections. Section 2 highlights on the literature work pertaining to the prediction of forest fire area. This is followed by section 3 where the background of the work is presented elaborating on the dataset used to carry out the empirical validation, ML techniques used for the development of prediction models and performance evaluation measures used in the study. Section 4 presents the results achieved in the work. Finally, the paper is concluded in section 5 which also highlights the scope for future work.

2. Literature Review

Analysis and prediction systems are widely used around the globe for predicting the fire, a measuring index called the FWI was started to be used by a European country which uses the meteorological data and a special behaviour prediction system has also been developed by an Asian country for incorporating satellite sensors. As they consider a vast variety of the suitable input factors, they are suited and often used for applications around the globe. These systems and their component variables enable the creation of datasets including historical data documenting a wide variety of current circumstances as well as geographical data connected to the total burnt area as a result of each occurrence [2]. Machine Learning (ML) algorithms seeking to estimate total burnt area on the basis of some specific condition, as well as data mining techniques to extract relevant information relating to specific incidents, can benefit from such datasets. When utilising such datasets, two major challenges are combining data from many sources and the strongly skewed nature of burnt area distributions. To create usable models, careful feature selection is required. Specific factors in certain areas are known to have a significant impact in the evaluation process [1].

Artificial Intelligence and regression methods have been used in the past to help in the estimation of areas where forest fires are prevalent and to what extent. Various models have been proposed to examine different aspects of environmental change that influence wildfire development [10]. Some specific methods that have been used are Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and regression models along with artificial Neural Networks (NN). These are used to draw conclusions and also for utilising some techniques which included fuzzy logics in order to draw predictions for total areas burnt by fires [5]. Wind field and environmental models have been used, improved upon by genetic algorithms. Classification of domains of relationships among datasets and probabilistic analysis are also being used [3]. A convolutional NN was used to construct a geospatial prediction model for susceptibility of forest fires that was indeed tallied archived data from some regions in Asia. In Indonesia, "ANFIS" has been used for classification of the areas which are more prone to forest fires. In some regions of Iran, some hybrid models which utilise the power of fuzzy logic to forecast the chance of wildfires have also been used [12].

However, there is still a lot of opportunity for advancement and development in terms of predicting the affected areas due to wildfires. As a fact, a lot of study and analysis has been done to investigate the possibilities of modern artificial intelligence and ML algorithms that avoid regressions, focusing instead on individual prediction

precision [2]. ML algorithms that have traditionally been used to determine and estimate the total affected areas due to these fires from algorithms which are based on data driven technologies including statistical distribution analysis, regression, correlation, etc with intermediate layers and computationally expensive calculations and approximations are playing role in the estimation of individual fire occurrences [5]. Unfortunately, these algorithms have not been very transparent in their calculations and approximations in order for us to apply data mining of the datasets which have been used in these models [13].

In this study, we enhance the popular Kaggle dataset using augmentation techniques through Google Earth Engine [14]. There have been many advancements until recent times to help predict the forest burnt area using ML algorithms but the need to train the models on robust datasets still remains.

3. Background of the Work

This section presents the background of the work relevant to carry the research in this paper. The explanation of the dataset used to carry out empirical analysis has been presented. This is followed by a brief overview of the ML techniques incorporated for the development of prediction models. Finally, evaluation measures have been explained.

3.1 Dataset Used

For the purpose of empirical validation, Kaggle Wildfire Dataset has been used in this study. The dataset has been used to examine and analyse the geographic locations of different wildfires that occurred in the United States in the late 20th century and starting of the 21st century that is from the years 1992 and 2015 [7]. The wildfire data was collected from central, state and local data on fires.

The dataset contains less than 2 million wildfire records (1.88 million wildfire records to be precise) covering a total of 140 acres of burnt land throughout a period of 24 years [15]. As is evident the size of the dataset is huge and applying ML algorithms on such dataset is computationally very expensive. Hence dataset was trimmed down to 21,833 entries which represent the forest fires for the state of Virginia in USA. The particular state has a dense set of data points concentrated around a particular geographic location (latitude and longitude). For our model to work efficiently we need to choose regions with high spatial density of data so that the latitude and longitude independently do not play a crucial role in regression. By choosing dense data space we can focus more on relevant features and the spatial identity of the locations will be on a relative stage and not impact the regression.

Figure 1 shows a sample of the original dataset with 7 independent variables (input ariables) viz. MyDate, Discovery_DOY, Fire_Year, FOD_ID, Stat_Cause_Code, Latitude, Longitude and 1 dependent variable (output variable) i.e., fire_size depicting the burnt area in acres. The independent variables have been explained below:

- MYDATE = It depicts the unique identifier for date on which the fire was discovered or confirmed to exist that contains information necessary to track back to the original record in the source dataset.
- DISCOVERY_DOY = It depicts the Day of year (1 to 365) on which the fire was discovered or confirmed to exist.
- FIRE_YEAR = It depicts the calendar year in which the fire was discovered or confirmed to exist.
- FOD_ID = It represents global unique identifier.
- STAT_CAUSE_CODE = It depicts the code for the (statistical) cause of the fire. Different classes of categories that might be the cause of the fire are arson, campfire, children, debris burning, equipment use, fireworks, lightning, powerline, railroad, smoking, structure, miscellaneous.
- lat = It depicts the latitude (NAD83) for point location of the fire (decimal degrees).
- lon = it depicts the longitude (NAD83) for point location of the fire (decimal degrees).

	MYDATE	DISCOVERY_DOY	FIRE_YEAR	FOD_ID	STAT_CAUSE_CODE	lat	lon	FIRE_SIZE
0	734873	5	2013	201842250	7	38.557778	-79.071667	4.0
1	734876	8	2013	201840578	3	38.300000	-79.383333	2.0
2	734876	8	2013	201840580	3	38.741389	-79.029444	2.0
3	734878	10	2013	201840757	3	36.854722	-82.447778	1.5
4	734891	23	2013	201840781	4	37.760278	-80.201944	0.5

Figure 1: Sample of original Kaggle wildfire dataset

Figure 2 shows the distribution of various classes of categories that might have been the cause of fire, which are dependent on various factors like geographic location, time of the year, etc. As can be seen from the figure, debris burning seems to be the main cause of fire. Figure 3 depicts graphical representation of the distribution of fire size (in acres) with the mean, median and variance of the fire size corresponding to Kaggle dataset. Number of fires represent the number of occurrences of a particular fire size.

Figure 2: Distribution of causes of fire

Mean fire size: 15.648139058543215
 Median fire size: 1.0
 Var in fire size: 46737.15855134302

Figure 3: Distribution of fire size (in acres) for Kaggle dataset

The limitation behind using the original Kaggle dataset is that it has only a few features (independent variables) which are not sufficient to achieve accurate prediction models. In order to overcome this limitation, the authors in this paper have augmented the original Kaggle dataset by the addition of new features, thus resulting in making a robust dataset which will lead to higher accuracy while training the prediction models.

We used spatially filtered dataset over the Virginia region in the USA and used existing APIs and Google Earth Engine (GEE) to create augmented values to enrich our exhaustive Kaggle dataset which was rich in data points but less in features. Figure 4 shows a sample of the augmented Kaggle dataset with the addition of four more new independent variables (input variables) viz. elevation_maximum, elevation_minimum, elevation_mean and slope_mean.

	MYDATE	STAT_CAUSE_CODE	elev_max	elev_mean	elev_min	slope_mean	lon	lat	FIRE_SIZE
0	734873	7	215	193.985950	168	18.022604	-79.071667	38.557778	4.0
1	734876	3	136	88.997007	57	20.427586	-79.383333	38.300000	2.0
2	734876	3	434	391.754443	348	17.098140	-79.029444	38.741389	2.0
3	734878	3	59	36.743952	-2	15.562330	-82.447778	36.854722	1.5
4	734891	4	680	507.770072	341	20.657843	-80.201944	37.790278	0.5

Figure 4: Sample of augmented Kaggle wildfire dataset

Adding features with topographical data readily available on APIs is a viable option. The features such as elevation_mean can be extracted and incorporated in the Kaggle dataset using geographical data available on APIs and we can also augment similar features like minimum elevation and maximum elevation from the APIs with the help of GEE scripts. After enriching the Kaggle dataset with ample and relevant features, we used this dataset along with the original dataset and compared the results obtained by training and applying prediction models on both the data collections.

3.2 Machine Learning Techniques Used

This section highlights on the different ML techniques used in the work for the development of prediction models. Brief explanation of each ML technique has been presented in Table 1.

Table 1: ML techniques used in the work

ML Technique Used	Explanation
Neural Network (NN)	NNs are based upon the structure of our human brains [16]. We can educate NNs to accomplish the same tasks on data as we can teach our brains to spot similarities and classify various kinds of data and information. NNs consist of different layers which are interconnected by a set of nodes. Individual layers of NNs may be thought of as a particular type of filter that operates from coarse to fine, increasing the chances of finding out and reaching a proper result [17, 18].
Support Vector Machine (SVM)	SVM is the most widely accepted classification algorithm. The objective of this algorithm is to find the decision boundary line (also called optimum line) for categorising a n-dimensional space into various distinct classes so when newer unknown data points appear, they may be placed in any of these classes [19,20]. The best possible plane for any such data points is called a hyperplane. The points or the vectors on the extremities that aid to identify and create a hyperplane are chosen via SVM.
Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)	MLP (which is a feed forward artificial NN) creates a set of outputs which are generated from a given collection of inputs [21]. An MLP is defined by numerous layers of input nodes that is represented as a directed graph [22].
K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN)	KNN is a regression technique which is a non-parametric approach that is used to approximate the relationship between all the independent variables against the continuous outcomes by averaging data (mean data) in the same neighbourhood/vicinity [23, 24]. Any analyst working on such regression must specify the size of the neighbourhood, or it may be decided using cross-validation in order to figure out the expected size that minimises the mean-squared error.
Decision Tree	It is used to construct regression or classification models. It slowly and gradually cuts down a whole dataset into smaller chunks/sections and while doing this it also develops a corresponding decision tree [25]. At

	the end of this process, a tree is derived which contains edges, decision nodes and leaf nodes.
Stacking Regressor	Stacking regression falls under the category of ensemble learning approach that uses a meta-regression to merge several regression models. Regression models are trained one by one using the entirety of the training set, and the outputs of the ensemble's individual regression models are used in the meta-regression.

3.3 Performance Evaluation Measures Used

This section elaborates on the different performance measures viz. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and R-Squared Error (R2) used to evaluate the performance of the prediction models developed using ML techniques on original Kaggle dataset as well as enhanced Kaggle dataset.

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

The Mean absolute Error (MAE) is one of the most popular measures used to study and quantify the model's performance in regression analysis [26]. It is used to assess the accuracy of a model's prediction to determine its quality. It is defined as the average of the absolute difference between the actual and anticipated values in the dataset. It calculates the average of the dataset's remaining residuals. MAE, being one of the widely used loss calculating functions for problems involving regression techniques, aids clients/users in transforming learning issues into optimization problems [27]. It also provides a simple, easy and quantifiable way to assess mistakes in regression issues. It is calculated using formula 1:

$$\mathbf{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - x| \quad (1)$$

Where:

- n = number of errors
- $|x_i - x|$ = the absolute errors
- R-Squared Error (R2)

R-squared error or R2 value generally lies between 0% - 100% in terms of percentage and between 0 and 1 in terms of score. R2 is the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables [28]. R-squared evaluates the dispersion of the data points around the fixed observation line. It is called "coefficient of determination", which is also applicable for more than one regression. In other words, it is the ratio of variance explained by the model and total variance.

The two extremities of R2 are 0% and 100%. 0% depicts that the model is poor and it is unable to express the variance of dependent variables around its average. 100% depicts that the model is efficient and is able to express the variance of the variable around its average in a very efficient manner. The goal while tailoring any regression model is to maximise the value of R2. The higher the value of the R-squared score is, the better the algorithm fits the observations. The R2 values are generally between 0 and 1 but a poor fitting model may also lead to negative R2 values [29].

4. Result Analysis

This section elaborates on the performance of different ML techniques when employed on both the original as well as enhanced Kaggle dataset used to develop the prediction models which will in future be useful for the prediction of area burnt due to forest fire. Table 2 depicts the performance of different ML techniques with respect to percentage error as the performance evaluation measure. As can be seen from table 2, percentage error of all the prediction models developed using ML techniques is less when employed on enhanced dataset as compared to the percentage error when employed on the original dataset. Thus, it can be concluded that the enhanced dataset

is more robust than the original dataset leading to higher accuracy in prediction. Another observation evident from the table is the MLP technique has performed best on original Kaggle dataset with minimum percentage error as 10 % and Decision Tree technique has performed best on enhanced dataset with only 3% percentage error.

Table 3 depicts the values of MAE (Mean Absolute Error) with respect to all the ML techniques when employed on original dataset and enhanced dataset. As we know, higher the MAE score of the model, lower the accuracy of the model leading to degraded performance of the model. As evident from table 3, the models trained on the augmented dataset have much lower MAE score than the models trained on the original dataset. This observation can lead to the conclusion that the new features viz. maximum elevation, minimum elevation, mean elevation and mean slope are more relevant features and including them in our original dataset has helped the models achieve better accuracy. Figure 5 illustrates the performance of the models with respect to MAE score on the enhanced dataset (depicted by orange colour bars) vis-à-vis their performance on the original dataset (depicted by blue colour bars). It is clearly visible that the models have performed exceptionally well on the enhanced dataset than on the original dataset.

Table 4 depicts the R2 score with respect to all the ML techniques when employed on original dataset and enhanced dataset. A higher R2 score is encouraged as an evaluation metric as a high R2 score confirms the reliability of a model. As can be seen from table 4, R2 scores are all negative with respect to original dataset. This indicates poor fitting in the model or the model does not follow the trend of the data. The R2 values are generally between 0 and 1 but a poorly fitting model may also lead to negative R2 values like in this case due to absence of relevant features. However, the models trained on the enhanced dataset results show splendid results with high R2 scores. Decision Tree technique which had the best MAE score out of all the other techniques for the augmented dataset has a R2 score of 0.93. Generally, in scientific studies an R2 value which is greater than or equal to 0.95 indicates a reliable model. We were able to achieve an R2 score of 0.97 using MLP technique on the enhanced dataset.

Table 2: Performance of Different ML Techniques with respect to Percentage Error

ML Technique used	PERCENTAGE ERROR (Original Kaggle dataset)	PERCENTAGE ERROR (Enhanced Kaggle dataset)
Neural Network	15%	14%
Support Vector Machine	11%	33%
Multi-Layer Perceptron	10%	12%
K-Nearest Neighbour	17%	23%
Decision Tree	21%	3%
Stacking Regressor	20%	15%

Table 3: Performance of Different ML Techniques with respect to MAE

ML Technique used	MAE (Original Kaggle Dataset)	MAE (Enhanced Kaggle Dataset)
Neural Network	22.11	5.83
Support Vector Machine	15.87	13.09
Multi-Layer Perceptron	23.66	5.00

K-Nearest Neighbour	25.59	9.07
Decision Tree	31.43	1.22
Stacking Regressor	28.66	6.12

Table 4: Performance of Different ML Techniques with respect to R squared Error

ML Technique used	R squared Error (Original Kaggle Dataset)	R squared Error (Enhanced Kaggle Dataset)
Neural Network	-0.23	0.91
Support Vector Machine	-0.01	0.72
Multi-Layer Perceptron	-0.04	0.97
K-Nearest Neighbour	-0.02	0.88
Decision Tree	-0.99	0.93
Stacking Regressor	-0.13	0.79

Figure 5: Performance of the ML techniques with respect to MAE values on the original dataset and enhanced dataset

As we expand our dataset and augment it with new features, dimensionality of the dataset also increases which may lead to inaccurate predictions. We can reduce dimensionality of the dataset by selecting the best features from features having high correlation. This can act as a dropout method for our model where we drop the irrelevant features to reduce overfitting. The authors in this work have used the correlation heatmap to the extract the best features from the original dataset as well as enhanced dataset. Figure 6 and 7 depicts the correlational heatmap for the features of the original dataset and enhanced dataset respectively which tells us about how different features are interrelated. Each pair of features has a connection represented by the rows. The strength of the association is shown by the values in the cells. Heatmaps of correlation can be used to identify possible links between variables

and to assess their strength. The value of the correlation coefficient can range from -1 (high negative relationship) to 1 (high positive relationship). Both linear and nonlinear associations between variables may be found using correlation heatmaps. The cells' colour coding makes it simple to see correlations between variables at a glance. Higher the intensity of the red colour between two features, more the strength between the two features. Similarly, as the intensity of blue colour increases, less is the strength between the two features. Therefore, the red colour signifies higher strength whereas the blue colour signifies lesser strength.

Correlation heatmaps play a crucial role to select the best features from the given features, thus reducing the dimensionality of the dataset. If two features have high correlation, one of the features can be dropped to reduce overfitting in the model as both of them will eventually follow the same trend and are linearly related to some extent, therefore they do not diversify the dataset.

It is visible from figure 6 that apart from the correlation between the same features that is always 1, there are no other features that show significant correlation between themselves. The derived features viz. elevation_max, elevation_mean and elevation_min are highly correlated (figure 7). This could be because they are being derived from the same data type i.e., 'elevation'. This implies that any two of these features could be dropped to reduce overfitting and training time. On the other hand, the derived feature i.e., slope_mean is not correlated highly with the other derived features and the probable cause could be that it is a different data type from elevation. This is in contrast to figure 6, where it can be seen that no two features are highly correlated because all the features in the original dataset are of different data types.

Figure 6: Cor-relation heatmap for the features of the original Kaggle dataset

Figure 7: Cor-relation heatmap for the augmented Kaggle dataset

The authors have used the `feature_selection` library from `sklearn` to rate the features on the basis of their relevance with respect to the output variable i.e., area burnt. A higher score means the feature is highly relevant and is a good choice for our prediction model.

Figure 8 shows the feature classification score of the features in the original Kaggle dataset with 'FOD_ID' feature having the highest score of 1.63. Figure 9 shows feature classification score of the features in the enhanced Kaggle dataset. Now the best features having high classification scores in the original Kaggle dataset are not considered best in the enhanced dataset as is evident from figure 9. Figure 9 shows that 'maximum elevation' feature is best with respect to the output variable (area burnt) having the highest classification score of 5.56 which is being followed by 'mean elevation' feature.

```
#Best Features - Univariate statistical selection
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2, f_classif, mutual_info_classif

feature_names = ['MYDATE', 'DISCOVERY_DOY', 'FIRE_YEAR', 'FOD_ID', 'STAT_CAUSE_CODE', 'lat', 'lon']

bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=f_classif, k=5)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,np.array(Y).astype(int))
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
df_specs = pd.Series(feature_names).astype(str)
featureScores = pd.concat([df_specs,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Feature','f_classif Score']
print(featureScores.nlargest(len(feature_names),'f_classif Score'))
```

	Feature	f_classif Score
3	FOD_ID	1.633780
2	FIRE_YEAR	1.378482
0	MYDATE	1.354870
4	STAT_CAUSE_CODE	1.268075
1	DISCOVERY_DOY	1.131915
6	lon	1.092921
5	lat	0.867531

Figure 8: Feature classification scores of specified features in original Kaggle dataset

```
#Best Features - Univariate statistical selection
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest
from sklearn.feature_selection import chi2, f_classif, mutual_info_classif

feature_names = ['MYDATE', 'STAT_CAUSE_CODE', 'elev_max', 'elev_mean', 'elev_min', 'slope_mean', 'lon', 'lat']

bestfeatures = SelectKBest(score_func=f_classif, k=5)
fit = bestfeatures.fit(X,np.array(Y).astype(int))
dfscores = pd.DataFrame(fit.scores_)
df_specs = pd.Series(feature_names).astype(str)
featureScores = pd.concat([df_specs,dfscores],axis=1)
featureScores.columns = ['Feature','f_classif Score']
print(featureScores.nlargest(5,'f_classif Score'))
```

	Feature	f_classif Score
0	DATE	1.135177e+08
2	elev_max	5.563171e+00
3	elev_mean	5.006158e+00
4	elev_min	4.024666e+00
1	STAT_CAUSE_CODE	1.633780e+00

Figure 9: Feature classification scores of specified features in enhanced Kaggle dataset

5. Conclusion and Future Scope

The need to develop systematic and adaptive models along with feature-rich datasets is essential to predict the area burnt due to forest fire and consequently take necessary actions by analysing the key factors that are involved in forest fires.

The study demonstrates the accurate prediction of forest fire burn size using the dataset having right number of features and by incorporating effective machine learning models. Data augmentation helped us attain a more reliable model for burn size prediction. While the original dataset along with machine learning algorithms served as a strong base for our research, adding on more relevant features using spatial data pertaining to the fire affected regions proved to be immensely beneficial for our study. This project serves as a prime example for data science driven predictors for natural phenomena. Higher accuracies were achieved in predicting forest fire burn area than the traditional models by adding an additional data mining and augmentation layer before the machine learning layer.

A special insight from the correlation heatmaps was drawn where high correlation was visible between three new features added in the augmented dataset (derived from elevation feature). This implied that any one of the features can be considered for developing the prediction models by dropping the remaining two features which will reduce overfitting and training time. As we expand our dataset and augment it with new features, we can reduce dimensionality of the model by using the best features from features having high correlation. This can act as a dropout method for the model where irrelevant features are dropped to reduce overfitting.

The authors also conducted a feature comparison which gave a measure of how important or relevant the feature is in predicting the output variable. This can be used to select the best feature or a combination of best features from the data to enhance the model in terms of data fitting and training time.

The results obtained have encouraged us to continue with our future research that intends to expand the study to incorporate parameters beyond elevation and slope. In addition to topography which has been considered in this study, there are different other parameters like drought, vegetation and weather which have been recommended by several other studies.

Secondly, it is argued that forest fires occur based on seasons if the causes are natural. It will be interesting to study phenomena using Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). Forest fires may happen due to a variety of phenomenon, accurate and reliable predictions is what the authors aim for and analyse it causes to a greater extent.

Thirdly, the authors aim to improve the prediction model with respect to their speed as well as accuracy. The authors would like to extend this project to add capabilities which help make onsite predictions using satellite extracted images. With the help of existing data on the affected regions and including more relevant features upon assessment, the authors aim to improve the accuracy and diversify the model to adapt to new scenarios, thus leading to more accurate and precise results.

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